

Date: 20/11/2025

Place: Fuente la Reina

We were contacted by Mr. Gerhard Weiss and Ms. Elaine Parlada of the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences in Vienna (BOKU), partners in Forwards with the European Forest Institute. They asked us if it was possible to visit an engagement activity within the framework of the MiMonte project. Mr. Wim Cambien, project leader of MiMonte, received Mss. Elaine Parlada in Valencia on November 20th for a lunch meeting, and shared our vision and way of working with her. Ms. Parlade then joined us for our tree-planting day on November the 22nd, to learn first-handed about the MiMonte project, see the engagement of volunteers and the outcome of this activity with volunteers. Photos taken by Ms. Parlade have been kindly shared with us, and used in our communication on this event and on the MiMonte project in general.

